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Abstract

This study explores non-invasive dendrochronology using X-ray computed tomography (CT) scanning as a method for dating and provenance determination of timber. The application of the technique is successfully demonstrated on medieval polychrome wooden sculptures. Subsequently, experimental work on consolidated archaeological wood is outlined, demonstrating the applicability of CT scanning for dendrochronology and for evaluating the treatment of waterlogged wood.

INTRODUCTION

A technique for non-invasive dendrochronology using X-ray computed tomography (CT) scanning was developed and refined by the main author and colleagues (Bill et al. 2012, Daly and Streeton 2017). The method was subsequently applied to a selection of late-medieval polychrome oak sculptures as part of analytical and material investigations, enabling dating and provenance identification of the timber used. The benefits of this technique were apparent, as it was possible to successfully date and provenance sculptures which had more than 80 preserved tree rings. Consequently, in order to push the boundaries of this technique, more complex material was selected for examination. In this manner, subsequent experimental work undertaken by Daly on archaeological wood treated with polyethylene glycol (PEG) revealed promising results for consolidated specimens, as described below.

BACKGROUND

Dendrochronology is extensively used in archaeology, conservation and related disciplines where precise dating of wooden objects and structures is required (e.g. altarpieces: Haneca et al. 2005; ships: Haneca and Daly 2014, Domínguez-Delmás et al. 2013; and buildings: Crone 2008). Usually, dendrochronology requires that samples of wood are taken or that exposed end-grain is prepared through paring of the surface in order to improve visualisation of the tree rings, thus making the technique invasive or micro-invasive. In comparison to this, non-invasive dendrochronology employing CT scanning provides the possibility of investigating wooden objects that do not have accessible or exposed end-grain, for example if covered in paint or in situations where it is unethical or undesirable to pare the wood. The non-invasive method had proven to be highly successful in previous studies (e.g. Bill et al. 2012, Daly and Streeton 2017), so it was expected that it would prove useful with other sculptures. However, no attempt had yet been made to scan conserved archaeological wood.

The sculptures initially examined using this non-invasive technique belonged to the collection of the Museum of Cultural History (MCH) at the University of Oslo in Norway and were formerly housed in churches in Troms county, northern Norway. These medieval sculptures were thought to originate in northern Germany and have in the past been dated stylistically to the late medieval period (Engelstad 1936). The sculptures included a *Female*

Figure 1. Female saint (90 × 26.5 × 15.5 cm): (a) recto, (b) verso and (c) X-ray, MCH, University of Oslo. Photos and X-ray image: Bettina Ebert

Figure 2. St Anne (58 × 26.3 × 13.6 cm): (a) recto, (b) verso, (c) timber joins marked and (d) X-ray, MCH, University of Oslo. Photos and X-ray image: Bettina Ebert

saint originally from Karlsøya island (Figure 1), a *Virgin and Nativity* sculpture from Torsken on Senja island and a *Bishop and Virgin and Child with Saint Anne* (hereafter called *St Anne*) (Figure 2), both from Berg on Senja island. The four sculptures examined in this study were of suitable size (less than 1.35 m in height) to fit into an industrial CT scanner, thus allowing non-invasive dendrochronology and visualisation of the internal wooden structure.

As a method for dating and identifying the provenance of the timber used in the construction of the sculptures, the technique was combined with additional material studies to describe aspects of the sculptures' biographies (see also Ebert 2017, 2018, 2019a, b). Updated scientific analyses of the sculptures employing current methods in dendrochronology and conservation science were considered important, given that dating and provenancing of the late-medieval corpus in Norway were last undertaken in the 1930s, albeit on a purely art-historical basis. Updated material investigations would allow new light to be shed on a hitherto understudied group of sculptures.

The conserved archaeological wood examined using the non-invasive technique was a barrel head found during excavation in the town of Odense, Denmark. Extensive excavations in Thomas B. Thriges Street were carried out between 2014 and 2017 by Odense City Museums, in advance of commercial development at the site. Dendrochronological analysis of the timber and wood from a wide range of structures found during the excavations attest to a range of activities in the town from the 11th to the 18th centuries, and this included several latrines and wells lined with re-used barrels. Almost all of the dendrochronological analyses of the site were carried out conventionally by sawing samples from selected timbers. However, it was decided not to damage this barrel head specifically, as it had a branded mark. Consequently, to discover the dating and origin of the tree used to make the object, non-invasive dendrochronology was considered a suitable method.

METHOD

Dendrochronology is a precise dating technique for wood through measurement and comparison of the timber's annual growth rings. These annual growth rings are formed in trees growing in temperate climates, and ring widths vary according to precipitation and temperature. (For an in-depth description of the method, see e.g. Baillie 1982 or Hillam 1998.) Trees of the same species growing in one region will exhibit a similar pattern of ring widths by virtue of being exposed to the same climate. Consequently, measurements of the growth rings can be cross matched with master chronologies in order to date the wood. Tree-ring series of more than approximately 80 continuous rings are usually required for successful dating. Furthermore, the technique also allows us to suggest the region where the tree grew. As it is the climate of a region that influences wood growth, the region of origin of the wood can also be determined.

An industrial CT scanner (Nikon Metrology XT H 225 LC) at the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI) in Oslo was used to examine the medieval sculptures. This scanner has micron resolution, which is much higher

than for medical CT scanners, therefore allowing precise measurement of tree rings (Bill et al. 2012). The scanner consists of a full protective enclosure and a 225 kV microfocus X-ray source with a reflection target and a 3 μm focal spot size. A 45 \times 45 cm^2 PerkinElmer flat panel detector with a 2048 \times 2048-pixel matrix is used for X-ray detection. The barrel head was scanned using a similar micro-CT scanning installation at the Technical University of Denmark. The virtual cross-sections were marked up using Adobe Photoshop and measured using Able Image Analyser software. The scale was used to calibrate the picture, so the measurements of the tree-ring widths are absolute measurements. For calculation of the correlation, Student's *t*-test (Student 1908) is used as the measure of similarity between the tree-ring datasets. For this, the *t*-value protocol CROS (Baillie and Pilcher 1973) is used, embedded in the DENDRO program (Tyers 1997).

The sculptures were positioned vertically on medium-density fibreboard stands and secured with cotton tape. The object rotated slowly through 360 degrees in front of the detector while a series of sequential digital X-ray images were taken, which were then assembled into a three-dimensional model. Each scan took approximately two hours. Individual slices or virtual cross-sections of the object could then be extracted and used as the basis for tree-ring measurements. In addition, internal structures and components could be visualised using the resultant CT scans either as two-dimensional cross-sections, or as three-dimensional tomographic reconstructions. The quality of the wood used was therefore also discernible and may contribute to greater understanding of internal construction features.

The dendrochronological method provides precise dating of the tree rings preserved in the wood. However, dating the exact felling year for the tree used requires that the complete sapwood be preserved, to the very last ring, under the bark. In practice this is rarely the case, as sapwood was commonly removed prior to wood use, and guild statutes often stipulated the use of heartwood only (Ulmann 1984, 105). For precise dating of the preserved wood, the amount missing has to be estimated to calculate the probable felling date of the tree. If any sapwood is preserved, then we know that we are not far from the original natural edge. Oak has a fairly consistent number of sapwood rings, depending on the region of origin of the timber. A range of sapwood estimates are therefore employed based on the geographical source identified for the timber under investigation, which provide an approximate felling date of the tree. In cases where no sapwood is preserved, it is only possible to provide a *terminus post quem*, or the earliest possible felling date, which is obtained by adding several years (to allow for missing sapwood) to the last measured tree ring.

RESULTS

Sculptures

Non-invasive dendrochronology was successful on all four sculptures scanned, allowing reliable measurements of the tree rings in all cases. The wood of the sculpture *Female saint* was successfully dated, as was the timber used for the *St Anne*, so the dating of these two case studies

will be discussed in detail here. No dates were achieved for the other two sculptures.

A single piece of oak was used for the carving of *Female saint*. Sapwood was preserved on the sculpture. It is clearly visible on the sculpture itself and on the resultant CT scans as lighter wood at the outermost rings (Figure 5). The tree-ring curve from the sculpture contains 98 measured tree rings, of which 9 are sapwood. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1387–1484. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree used in this sculpture can consequently be placed at AD 1490–1505. As the tree used grew in the northern German region, a sapwood statistic for northern Germany was used. Oak trees here have an average of approximately 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980).

Based on correlation values between the tree-ring curve and various known chronologies, it was possible to achieve high correlation with a master chronology for Lübeck (Table 1). This indicates that the sculpture could have been made from an oak tree that grew in the vicinity of Lübeck, supporting the art-historical conclusions.

Table 1. C3124 *Female saint* from Karlsøya island, Troms. Correlation between the tree-ring curve for the sculpture and diverse northern European sites and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given in parentheses. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values

File name	Chronology start date	Chronology end date	<i>Female saint</i> Karlsøya C3124 Z162001a	Chronology name (source)
–			AD 1387	
–			AD 1484	
Master chronologies				
DM100008	AD 457	AD 1723	8.40	Lübeck (Hamburg Univ.)
DM100007	AD 1080	AD 1967	5.84	Hamburg (Hamburg Univ.)
DM200005	AD 915	AD 1873	5.77	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Univ.)
Site chronologies				
H112UM01	AD 1391	AD 1543	10.20	Niendorf, Dörpstraat, 6 timbers (Hamburg Univ., revised Daly 2007)
H11HHM01	AD 1379	AD 1531	7.61	Lübeck, Langer Lohberg, 14 timbers (Hamburg Univ., revised Daly 2007)
H110GM01	AD 1386	AD 1511	7.60	Behlendorf, Seestr., 10 timbers (Hamburg Univ., revised Daly 2007)
H1110M01	AD 1423	AD 1541	6.43	Lübeck, Engelswisch, 4 timbers (Hamburg Univ., revised Daly 2007)
H111XM01	AD 1394	AD 1539	6.12	Lübeck, Tuenkenhagen, 6 timbers (Hamburg Univ., revised Daly 2007)
Oak for artworks				
Z104101&103a	AD 1369	AD 1470	8.02	Skjervøy sculptures, Virgin & Olav same tree CT (Daly and Streeton 2017)
Shipwrecks and cargos				
00651m07lubeck	AD 1386	AD 1586	6.43	Copenhagen ship, B&W1, 2 timbers (Daly 1997a; 2007)
Z093M001	AD 1420	AD 1614	5.92	Vasa barrels, 7 timbers (Daly 2013a)

Due to the relatively broad width of the *St Anne* sculpture, scanning was undertaken in two stages in order to visualise as many sequential tree rings as possible. The sculpture was found to consist of three oak boards glued together (Figure 2c).

Figure 3. Illustration of the chronological position of the dated wood elements for two sculptures from the MCH collection. Red shading indicates the dating of the felling of the trees used for *St Anne*, while the blue shading indicates the felling dating for the tree used for *Female saint*. Illustration: Aoife Daly

Figure 4. Virtual cross-section of the *St Anne* sculpture, in two parts, marked and ready for measurement. Image: Heidi Debreczeny Wilkinson and Bjørnar Slensvik, NGL; markings during analysis: Aoife Daly

Figure 5. (a) Close-up photo and (b) virtual slice of *Female saint*, with sapwood clearly visible. Photo: Aoife Daly; image: Heidi Debreczeny Wilkinson and Bjørnar Slensvik, NGL; markings during analysis: Aoife Daly

The wooden element at the front of the sculpture contains 138 tree rings, with only heartwood observed. Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree used for this element was felled after AD 1425 (Figure 3). The wood for the middle piece is from a very slow-growing tree, with an average annual growth rate of just 1.05 mm per year (Figure 4). The middle element contains 223 tree rings and is from a tree felled after AD 1432 (Figure 3). From the CT imagery, it was possible to count and measure 186 tree rings on the wood at the back. The CT-scan imagery did not cover the full width of this part. Approximately 10 heartwood rings were present but were not measured from the outermost position. Observations of the sculpture surface confirmed that a little sapwood was also present, though these rings could not be counted or measured. The estimated dating for the felling of the tree used for the wood at the back can be placed at ca. AD 1471–85 (marked with red in Figure 3). As the trees for the wood elements making up the sculpture probably grew in the Baltic region (see below), a sapwood statistic for northern Poland was used. Oak trees here have an average of 15 sapwood years (-6+9) (Wazny 1990).

Baltic boards or wainscot were imported in huge numbers as raw material to many central European regions during the Middle Ages. A cargo of boards found in the so-called Copper Wreck (found in the Bay of Gdansk and dating to the 1410s) demonstrates that several sizes of board were shipped (Ossowski 2014). We see these used for items such as barrels, panelling, boat planks and for ecclesiastical furniture, though their use for the actual sculptures is less common. Details relating to this unique composite block construction technique are discussed elsewhere (Ebert 2017).

Dating by means of dendrochronology correlated fairly well with the stylistic dating of the sculptures: *Female saint* had been dated by Engelstad (1936) to the 1520s and *St Anne* to the 1470s. Two of the four scanned sculptures (*Virgin and Nativity* and *Bishop*) could not be dated unfortunately due to insufficient uninterrupted tree rings. However, wooden defects and the internal construction of the sculptures were clearly visualised using the CT scans, and these facilitated technical comparisons with other sculptures. *Virgin and Nativity* was found to have been carved out of poor-quality wood, with knots, defects and extensive woodworm damage (Ebert 2019b). *Bishop*'s construction was very different from that of *St Anne*, something which, in addition to further material differences, supported the hypothesis that the sculptures were not related, despite previous suggestions by art history scholars in the 1930s (Ebert 2018).

Barrel head

As a next step in examining further situations in which this non-invasive dendrochronological technique could be employed, testing was undertaken on consolidated archaeological wood. A lid of a barrel (Figure 6), recently found during archaeological excavations in Odense in Denmark, was fully consolidated using a combination of PEG (polyethylene glycol 2000, 38%) and freeze-drying post-excavation (Aagaard pers. comm.). The question here was if imaging of the wood anatomy would be possible using CT scanning to enable reliable tree-ring measurement, as the density of the PEG was similar to that of wood. The barrel lid was supported upright by a wooden

Figure 6. Odense barrel head after consolidation. Photo: Aoife Daly

Figure 7. Odense barrel head, virtual slice. Image: Carsten Gundlach, DTU

Table 2. C2912 *St Anne*, from Berg church, Senja island, Troms. Correlation between the tree-ring curves for the sculpture and diverse northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values

File name	Chronology start date	Chronology end date	<i>St Anne</i> Berg back Z163001a	<i>St Anne</i> Berg mid & front Z163M001	Chronology name (source)
–			AD 1267	AD 1200	
–			AD 1452	AD 1422	
Master chronologies					
OM040004	AD 1156	AD 1597	4.94	6.98	Baltic 1, 64 timbers (Hillam and Tyers 1995)
PP122M01	AD 1006	AD 1359	1.61	5.05	Elblag, 114 timbers (Wazny pers. comm., revised Daly 2007)
Baltic oak for artworks					
Z103009&10	AD 1290	AD 1488	3.50	8.23	Slagen altarpiece, Norway, right wing, bottom relief (Daly 2013c)
Z0800039	AD 1275	AD 1512	2.01	7.20	Painted panel 'Moneylenders' plank 3 (Daly 2011c, Daly and Läänelaid 2012)
Z0700019	AD 1238	AD 1436	5.66	2.56	Bouts, painted panel 'Madonna with child' (Daly 2011b)
Shipwrecks and cargo of Baltic oak					
Z054m001	AD 1235	AD 1448	3.26	8.07	Ostsee VII, Mönchgut, FPL92, ship planks, 5 timbers (Daly 2010)
0075M0012012	AD 1113	AD 1463	6.06	6.05	Vejdyb ship, 16 timbers (Daly 1997b & unpubl.)
02070169	AD 1200	AD 1390	0.74	5.47	Dokøen, Copenhagen, ship 3 (Eriksen 2001)
02071059	AD 1201	AD 1412	6.27	3.63	Dokøen, Copenhagen, ship 2 (Eriksen 2001)
se613m01	AD 1197	AD 1464	5.86	2.51	Hull, Blaydes Staithe, 3 timbers (Tyers pers. comm.)
Z084007a	AD 1338	AD 1435	5.53	3.37	Skaftö wreck, barrel head (Daly 2013b)

stand, in much the same way as the procedure for the sculptures. To optimise the resolution, the object was scanned in three sections (a virtual slice of the first scan is shown in Figure 7). As can be seen, clear images were obtained in this first experiment, which also allowed observation of the depth of penetration of the consolidant. It was clear, from the image produced, that in this example the PEG had not penetrated through the full depth of the preserved wood, so that in fact the highest clarity of the tree rings was achieved along the object core. Along the edges where PEG had penetrated, the tree rings were still discernible but not nearly as clearly. If the wood had been in less solid condition (wood from more ancient remains, for example), the PEG might have penetrated the material more deeply, which could have proven challenging.

This barrel head from Odense contained 217 tree rings and the curve was dated. No sapwood was observed, so the felling of the tree used took place after ca. AD 1332. Correlation between the barrel and diverse northern European oak chronologies showed that this timber matched a range of datasets for Poland (Table 3). (Several other barrel parts from the excavation at Odense that were analysed conventionally were also shown to be of southern Baltic origin, while other barrels found in the excavation

Table 3. Barrel head, Thomas B. Thriges Street, Odense. Correlation between the tree-ring curve from the barrel head and diverse northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values

File name	Chronology start date	Chronology end date	Barrel head OBM9776 x1813 Z1216038	Chronology name (source)
–			AD 1106	
–			AD 1322	
Master chronologies				
PP114M01	AD 1152	AD 1447	6.29	Poland, Gdansk, Wole Rogi, 18 timbers (Wazny pers. comm., revised Daly 2007)
P822001m	AD 1185	AD 1320	6.27	Poland, Malbork, (Wazny pers. comm.)
DM100008	AD 457	AD 1723	5.70	Lübeck (Hamburg Univ.)
PP111M01	AD 1136	AD 1399	5.68	Poland, Gdansk, St Nikolaus, 11 timbers (Wazny pers. comm., revised Daly 2007)
PP147M01	AD 1151	AD 1363	5.64	Poland, Jeziernik, 10 timbers (Wazny pers. comm., revised Daly 2007)
PP118M01	AD 1112	AD 1399	5.51	Poland, Gdansk, various sites, 31 timbers (Wazny pers. comm., revised Daly 2007)
Shipwrecks and cargo of Baltic oak				
D013551&52	AD 1077	AD 1302	5.93	Odense, Thomas B. Thriges Street, barrel, 2 timbers (Daly & Daly 2019)
Z056m001	AD 1065	AD 1266	5.71	Egelskärsvraket, Finland, barrel, 4 timbers (Daly 2011a)
0056M001	AD 1174	AD 1335	5.52	Aberdeen, barrel (Crone pers. comm.)
Z005M003	AD 1063	AD 1373	5.35	Bølevraget, planks, 4 timbers (Daly and Nymoen 2008)
Z220M001	AD 1137	AD 1313	5.28	Stenstruppgård, barrels, 9 timbers (Daly 2018)
D0132M02	AD 1096	AD 1336	5.28	Odense, Thomas B Thriges Street, staves, 7 timbers (Daly 2016)
se617M01	AD 1100	AD 1396	5.12	New Baxtergate, Grims, 5 timbers (Sheffield Univ., revised Daly 2007)
doel2_m2	AD 1161	AD 1296	5.11	Ship timbers, Doel 2 (Vermeersch et al. 2015)
60132M02	AD 1145	AD 1368	5.09	Boringholm, barrels, 2 lids & 3 staves (Daly 2005)

demonstrated that goods had also come from other sources.) The barrel head examined here also correlated well with many other barrels and shipwrecks from the period from this south Baltic source (Daly 2011d). This barrel head represents the beginnings, in the 14th century, of the oak trade that we see represented widely in the dendrochronological record, not least for the ecclesiastical art industry. Cargos of timber in shipwrecks demonstrate that not only were southern Baltic barrels containing goods shipped westwards but that the wood itself, as clapboard, was also traded.

FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

Studies still need to be conducted on how this very positive result compares to older consolidation campaigns using PEG on archaeological wood, or wood conserved with other techniques. It is clear, however, that CT scanning for dendrochronology provides an opportunity for conservation and heritage specialists to use the imagery for other purposes (for example to evaluate the condition of wooden artefacts in museum collections or to observe the success of consolidation). New experiments involving the scanning of waterlogged wood are beginning to produce positive results. The analysis is of course more costly than analysing invasively, both in the time that it takes

and in the cost of using the equipment. Transport costs can also be an issue, as the objects must be brought to a suitable machine. A growing database of installations is available at <http://microctworld.net/> (accessed November 2019) listing commercial and research-based locations and manufacturers.

CONCLUSION

The use of CT scanning in undertaking non-invasive dendrochronology has proven to be a highly successful method in line with developing trends towards non-invasive analysis whenever possible. In addition to aiding dendrochronology, industrial CT scanners with sufficient resolution enable detailed visualisation of the internal structure of imaged wooden objects, while also aiding observation of the penetration depth of PEG-treated archaeological wood.

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